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Technical Report No. 209

Flow over rough topography.

A preliminary study
with high resolution topography at Ormen Lange

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December 1, 2001

Deliverance for Task 2 to Norsk Hydro
Contract No. NHT-B44-5113464-0

Executive summary

Ormen Lange is an offshore gas field located in the Storegga region on the Norwegian west coast. The field is located at the sea bed with the depth varying from 600m to 1100m. In this report we focus on the current conditions just above a 400x400m large square located at approximately 670m depth, by doing simulations with a sigma co-ordinate ocean model. We apply a horizontal resolution of 4m, which is extremely high for this class of models. In the vertical we use a resolution gradually increasing from 2m up to 50m in the top layer, with more than 60 percent of the points for the lowest 100meters.

We found the model to give reasonable and realistic response to the topography by using large horizontal viscosities for the momentum equations, but we were not able to march as long in time as desired, due to stability issues. On the given topography an amplification of the background flow up to 20 percent was predicted.

Plots showing amplification factors for selected horizontal sections, after imposing a constant velocity flow over the given topography are presented, as well as vertical velocity profiles at selected locations.

1 Introduction

The challenging task of placing oil installations on several hundred meters depth has increased the focus on the ocean dynamics on the west coast of Norway. The Ormen Lange field has for several years proven to be interesting both to engineers from the oil industry and oceanographers, due to the highly dynamic features of the flow. As we can see in Figure 1 the depth of the Ormen Lange field is varying from a few hundred meters to more than 1000 meters, and the topography is abrupt due to ancient geological events such as the Storegga slide about 8000 years ago.

The flow over our domain of interest to a large extent follows the bottom topography, and the properties of the watermasses have large variability. Several articles and reports discuss the conditions in this area, see for instance reports by Eliassen, Eldevik, Berntsen and Furnes [4], [5] and [3]. In this report topographical effects are investigated by applying a three dimensional sigma co-ordinate ocean model to a domain using very high horizontal resolution. The area is 400m by 400m horizontally, and the depth varies between 643m to 687m. The location is indicated with a black square in Figure 1.

The sigma co-ordinate model is stepped forward in time using a mode splitting

Figure 1: The location of the Ormen Lange field and the small domain investigated in this report

technique, short time steps for the barotropic depth integrated part and longer time steps for the remaining three dimensional baroclinic part.

The focus of this work has been to look at micro-scale effects of abrupt bottom topography by setting up a simple experiment where we let horizontally homogeneous water-masses with vertical salinity and temperature profiles initially taken from measurements, flow with a near constant background velocity over the topography.

The model choice is interesting because hydrostatic sigma co-ordinate models are normally applied to cases where the typical horizontal length scales are much larger than the vertical scales. In this particular case, the two scales are of the same order of magnitude while the actual dimensions of the domain are larger in the vertical than the horizontal.

The model also uses a free surface formulation, giving a limitation on the allowed time step, surface waves are traveling with a speed of $\sqrt{gH} \approx 80m/s$. On the other hand this kind of model is much more effective computationally than non-hydrostatic type of models, giving an opportunity to increase e.g. model size

or resolution in time and space.

2 Model setup

The model used in the experiments was a mode splitted, hydrostatic sigma coordinate ocean model [1], created at the University of Bergen and the Institute of Marine research, on which development started around 1995. The model can be run with both implicit and mode-splitted algorithms to handle the coupling between the 2D depth integrated part, related to surface waves, and the 3D baroclinic part.

It was first our intention to neglect the effect of the surface gravity waves, that travel with a velocity that can be several thousand times larger in magnitude than the three dimensional velocities of the watermasses near the bottom. Possible options for this approach could be to use the same time-step for all components of the model and solve the surface gravity waves implicitly in time, marching forward with Courant number of magnitude 1000. The second major option could be to use a mode splitted approach, marching all parts of the model forward in time explicitly, but each part obeying its respective CFL condition, which would mean using the model almost as a 2D model since several thousand 2D steps would be used per 3D step.

Both approaches, however, turned out to be too difficult due to the fact that surface waves moves so fast. To be efficient we want to use as long steps as possible for the 3D mode, which is the main interest in this study, however, this gives a very large number of time-steps for the 2D mode. We experience that the free surface solution during all the 2D steps changes so rapidly that the 3D model experiences the changes in e.g. elevation as a periodic motion with period $2\Delta T$. As the vertical velocity is proportional to terms in the sigma coordinate model with the time derivative of elevation, this effect forced us to reduce the number of 2D steps per 3D step down to 40. Not doing this would yield unrealistically large vertical velocities. With moderate supercomputing resources, we can now simulate a few hours. With the large viscosities used in this experiment this seems to be sufficient to catch the major transients. With lower viscosities we could probably observe internal wave phenomena with a few days as the timescale, and it would be practical with a way to get around the above problem with large vertical velocities, in order to reduce the computing time.

2.1 Bottom matrix

Figure 2 shows a contour map of the topography of our domain. We observe that the area is occupied with small hills and valleys with typical height of 15 meters, and a horizontal size of maybe 50 meters. The bottom matrix was constructed by first triangulating raw data from Norsk Hydro, then using cubic polynomials interpolating this to a 1m resolution mesh which was used to construct meshes of subregions with 1,2 and 4 meter resolution. For the locations marked 1,2,3 and 4

Figure 2: Depth in meters. Locations for vertical profiles marked 1,2,3 and 4. Units for X and Y axes are meters.

in Figure 2 we save vertical profiles of velocity, salinity and temperature. These

locations are close to meters placed by Norsk Hydro.

2.2 Grid

The horizontal grid is uniform and with 4m resolution. Normally this kind of models have horizontal resolution of a few kilometers.

The vertical grid was generated by an automatic tool giving a smooth transition from the 2m bottom resolution up to the $\approx 50\text{m}$ top layer resolution, with more than 60 percent of the points for the lower 100 meters. The vertical distribution of grid points can also be seen in Figure 19.

2.3 Initial conditions

Initial velocity is 0m/s. Initial temperature and salinity are horizontally homogeneous and stratified, with vertical profiles interpolated from the measured profiles in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Vertical distribution of the initial salinity and temperature. Depth given in meters, Temperature in degrees centigrade, Salinity in PSU.

The horizontal viscosity are initially constant, model parameters for BOM are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} AM &= 0.5 \\ AM2D &= 20 \\ AH &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where AM and AM2D are horizontal viscosities given in m^2/s for the momentum equations 3D and 2D depth integrated part respectively. AH is the horizontal diffusivity for transport equations for salinity and temperature. A mixing length model due to Smagorinsky [8] is used to estimate horizontal eddy viscosities for the momentum equations, ensuring that the viscosity at no time is larger than $0.0625 * DX * *2/DT$, where DX and DT are the grid spacing in meters and 3D time-step in seconds respectively. The Mellor Yamada turbulence closure [7] is used to compute the vertical eddy viscosities.

2.4 The boundary conditions and spin-up

The model is forced without wind stress, with standard quadratic bottom stress as found in the Princeton Ocean Model [2] and described in the report by Berntsen et. al. [1]. No heat flux at the surface. Lateral boundary conditions are handled through the Flow Relaxation Scheme (FRS) [6], the FRS zone is seven cells wide on all sides.

The lateral boundary conditions for velocity are as follows: If we let α be the angle between the velocity and the X axis (axis going eastward in Figure 2) and t be the time in hours we have:

$$\kappa(t) = t/T_{Spinup} \quad (1)$$

$$U(t) = 0.02\kappa \cos(\alpha) \max(H_U)/H_U \quad (2)$$

$$V(t) = 0.02\kappa \sin(\alpha) \max(H_V)/H_V \quad (3)$$

In the first experiment $\alpha = 45^\circ$, that is we impose a constant background flow in from the south-west.

Elevation is kept equal to zero throughout the whole simulation in the FRS zones. This is the reason why velocity everywhere in the FRS zone is scaled with the fraction of depth over maximum depth. Barotropic waves propagate through the domain in just a few seconds, so by defining T_{Spinup} to be e.g. 3 seconds, we will during these first seconds of a simulation let the velocity in the 7 cell wide FRS zones be increased linearly towards the chosen background velocity.

The 3D time step for all experiments was 0.9 seconds, and the number of 2D steps per 3D (baroclinic) step was 36.

3 Results

Figure 5 shows the time series of the velocity and elevation in point 1, on the top of one of the small seamounts at approximately 660m depth. We observe that the velocity, which initially is zero, in about 10 seconds reaches the magnitude of the driving velocity in the FRS zone, and after some initial oscillations reaches a steady level after about 15 minutes (1000 seconds). In the time series of kinetic energy in Figure 4, we observe that the kinetic energy of the interior stabilizes after only 20 seconds, slightly after velocity has reached its level in point 1.

Figure 6 shows the vertical profiles of salinity and temperature after 1 hour, comparing them with the initial profiles in Figure 3 we observe that there is not much difference.

In figures 7-16 we have plotted horizontal sections of what we call the gain factor, i.e. the velocity divided by the imposed background velocity. Some gain is implicitly given by the topography since the maximum depth is approximately 6 percent larger than the minimum. We observe that as expected the gain is larger than one over the small seamounts, and smaller than one over the troughs.

The gain factor is plotted for horizontal sections 2,5,10 and 50 meters above the bottom. From the figures we observe that the largest gain after one hour is about 18 percent, we also have a reading of 20, but it is not reliable since it is in a corner very close to the FRS zone. The FRS zone is seven cells wide, and we may in most of the figures observe that the effect of this zone also is visible a few more cells into the domain.

Figure 19 shows the vertical cross section going from west to east through the center of the domain. We see the expected similarity with 2D potential flow solutions over small amplitude topography.

Figures 21 to 24 show the vertical profiles in four selected locations marked in Figure 2. As seen in Figure 2 points 1 and 2 are located on top of two hills, point 3 in the small dump slightly behind point 1 with respect to the direction of the flow, while point 4 is located inbetween the two hills 1 and 2. What we expect to see in plots of vertical profiles are the blocking effect due to topography accelerating the flow over sea-mounts, and the bottom friction should generate a boundary layer with reduced velocity. We also expect to see a tendency for a small wake to form in the profiles of point 3.

The effects of positions of stations on the vertical profiles of velocity near to the bottom are clearly seen in Figure 20, from a simulation without bottom friction. If we compare these plots with the profiles in figures 21 to 24, we see that the only major difference is the clear appearance of the bottom boundary layer in the simulations including friction.

Figure 4: Time development of volume averaged kinetic energy [Jm^{-3}]. Time axis unit is seconds.

Figure 5: Time series of U [m/s] and η [m] in point 1, 5m above bottom

Figure 6: Vertical profile of Salinity[PSU] and Temperature[°C] after 1hr in point 1

Figure 7: Gain factor for velocity 2m above bottom with 5cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 8: Gain factor for velocity 2m above bottom with 10cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 9: Gain factor for velocity 2m above bottom with 20cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 10: Gain factor for velocity 5m above bottom with 5cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 11: Gain factor for velocity 5m above bottom with 10cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 12: Gain factor for velocity 5m above bottom with 20cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 13: Gain factor for velocity 10m above bottom with 5cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 14: Gain factor for velocity 10m above bottom with 10cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 15: Gain factor for velocity 10m above bottom with 20cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 16: Gain factor for velocity 50m above bottom with 5cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 17: Gain factor for velocity 50m above bottom with 10cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 18: Gain factor for velocity 50m above bottom with 20cm/s background velocity. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 19: Velocity [m/s] in the vertical section from west to east through the center of the domain, after 1hr simulation with a background velocity of 20cm/s. X and Y axis units in meters

Figure 20: Absolute velocity [m/s] without bottom friction in point 1,2 and 3

Figure 21: Absolute velocity [m/s] in point 1 for the three background velocities

Figure 22: Absolute velocity [m/s] in point 2 for the three background velocities

4 Conclusions

In this report we discuss the findings of applying a sigma co-ordinate ocean model with high horizontal resolution of 4 meters, to a domain 400x400 meters horizontally and approximately 670 meters deep.

The flow is horizontally homogeneous, but stratified, using the salinity and temperature profiles from measurements. A constant south west flow of varying strength is imposed to the model, and the surface elevation is allowed to vary freely in the interior of the domain, forcing it towards zero on the boundaries.

We found the model to give reasonable and realistic response to the topography by using large horizontal viscosities for the momentum equations, but we were not able to march as long in time as desired, due to stability issues. On the given topography a magnification of the background flow up to 20 percent was predicted.

Future studies should focus on getting rid of the dependency of the surface processes in order to march with longer time steps. If effects like internal waves or shedding behind the small seamounts are desired, one should consider using non-hydrostatic models. It will also be necessary to use lower values for viscosities to

Figure 23: Absolute velocity [m/s] in point 3 for the three background velocities

avoid filtering out interesting dynamical phenomena, but this is very challenging as we already are near/have crossed the limits of applicability for this type of models. Note that the problem with very fast moving surface gravity waves is challenging for most (all) fluid models.

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Figure 24: Absolute velocity [m/s] in point 4 for the three background velocities

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